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Impact of different fungicides and bio-agents on management of spot blotch of wheat caused by *Bipolaris sorokiniana* (Sacc.) Shoemaker

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Abstract

Field experiment was conducted at Research Farm of PG college Ghazipur For the management of spot blotch disease of wheat. One bio-agent, one bioenhancer and seven fungicides were used. Plant disease intensity decreased with the application of different treatment over untreated control. Minimum plant disease intensity was recorded (21.00% first year and 20.70% second year) under T₉ (Seed treatment with Raxil @ 2.5 gm/kg seed + 2 foliar sprays of propiconazole @ 0.1%, first at boot leaf stage second after 20 days), Maximum plant disease intensity was recorded (71.80% first year and 74.00% second year) under T₁₁ (Control), Which has highly significant compared to all the treatments. Maximum grain yield was recorded (39.05 q/ha and 39.25 q/ha first and second year) and maximum thousand seed weight was recorded (42.05g and 42.40g first and second year) under T₉ (Seed treatment with Raxil @ 2.5 gm/kg seed + 2 foliar sprays of propiconazole @ 0.1%, first at boot leaf stage second after 20 days), Minimum grain yield was recorded (31.25q/ha and 31.04q/ha during the both year) and least thousand seed weight was recorded(36.30g and 36.18g during 2018-19 and 2019-20) under T₁₁ (Control).

Keywords: Fungicides, bio-agents, spot, *Bipolaris sorokiniana*

Introduction

Cereals serve a critical role in meeting the world's rising population's food needs, particularly in developing countries where cereal-based manufacturing is the norm system is the only predominant source of nutrition and calorie intake. The nutrient-rich cereal is grown in diversified environments; and globally wheat occupies around 216.95 million hectares (mha) holding the position of highest acreage among all crops with an annual production covering around 764.11 metric tonnes (mt) last year (Feldman, 2001)^[4]. Moreover, it provides almost half of all calories in the region of North Africa and West and Central Asia Wheat, along with rice, is one of the most important sources of protein in least developed and middle-income countries, both in terms of calories and dietary intake. The crop is cultivated mostly in winter and spring seasons around the world; it being grown in winter in cold countries like Europe, USA, Australia, Russian Federation, etc., while in spring in countries of Asia and in some parts of the USA.

In India, production of Wheat during 2019-20 is estimated at record 107.18 million tonnes. It is higher by 3.58 million tonnes as compared to wheat production during 2018-19 and is higher by 11.02 million tonnes than the average wheat production of 96.16 million tones as per the recent 3th Advance Estimates from Directorate of Economics and Statistics (DES), Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare (MoA&FW), India (2020). The production of wheat has also showed an increasing trend, from 99.9 to 103.6 million tonnes from 2018-2019 to 2019-2020 with a magnitude of 3.7 million tones. The major source of this increase in production is mainly attributed to expansion in area followed by marginal increase in productivity. Uttar Pradesh still holds the position of largest producer in the country accounting for about 28 million tonnes which is roughly 30% of the total production. Around 85 million tonnes (90%) of wheat has been produced from traditional wheat-growing regions such as Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Bihar and Rajasthan. Wheat provides nearly 55% of carbohydrate and 20% of the food calories. It contains carbohydrate 78.10%, protein 14.70%, fat 2.10%, minerals 2.10% and considerable proportions of vitamins (thiamine and vitamin-B) and minerals (zinc, iron) calcium (37 mg/100g), iron (4.1 mg/100g), thiamine (0.45mg/100g), riboflavin (0.13mg/100g) and nicotinic acid (5.4mg/100mg). Among all the diseases, spot blotch of wheat is considered as one of the most important disease in environments which are characterized by high temperature (coolest month greater than 17°C) and high humidity.

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Globally, an estimated 25 million hectares of wheat cultivated land is affected by spot blotch disease (van Ginkel and Rajaram, 1998) [18]. Due to drastic changes in climatic conditions in the last two or three decades, spot blotch has emerged as a major threat to wheat production in India. Spot blotch is affecting nearly 9 mha of the warm North-Eastern Plain Zone where millions of resource-poor farmers grow wheat after rice (Joshi *et al.*, 2004) [6]. The disease is gradually extending towards the North-West, the major wheat growing areas in the country (Chand *et al.*, 2003) [3].

Materials and Methods

This experiment was conducted during *Rabi* season 2018-19 and 2019-20 MES, P.G. College Ghazipur, Uttar Pradesh. Eleven treatment *viz* T₁ Seed treatment with Thiram @ 3g/kg seed, T₂ Seed treatment with Tebuconazole @ 2.5g/kg seed, T₃ Seed treatment with *Trichoderma viride* @ 4 g/kg seed, T₄ Two foliar spray of Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% @ 0.4% T₅ Two foliar spray of Jeevamrit @ 5%, 7.5% and 10% concentration T₆ Two foliar spray of Copper oxychloride @ 0.1% T₇ Two foliar spray of Hexaconazole @ 2.5% T₈ T₁ + Two foliar spray of Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% @ 0.4% T₉ T₂ + Two foliar spray of Propiconazole @ 0.1% T₁₀ T₃ + Two foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 0.1% and T₁₁ Untreated (unsprayed) were tested for management of spot blotch disease in randomized block design with three replications observations on different traits were recorded and the results thus obtained are discussed under results and discussion.

Results and Discussion

During 2018-19 for the management of foliar blight disease of wheat seed dresser fungicides and bioagents *viz*. Thiram 50 WP @ 2.5g/kg of seeds, Tebuconazole @ 2.5g/kg of seeds and *Trichoderma viride*, foliar spray fungicides Propiconazole @ 0.4%, Tebuconazole 50%+Trifloxystrobin in 25% @ 0.4%/lit., Hexaconazole @ 0.1%, Copper oxychloride @ 0.1% and one bio-enhancer Jeevamrit @ 2.5ml were used singly or in combination of seed treatment plus foliar spray. The minimum per cent disease intensity was recorded with T₉ (21.00%) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (22.50%), T₈ (23.60%) and T₄ (24.40%) and significantly followed by T₇ (25.70%) T₆ (31.40%), T₅ (32.80%), T₂ (35.60%), T₁ (31.10%) and T₃ (36.80%). Maximum per cent disease intensity (71.80%) was recorded under T₁₁ untreated (control plot) (Table-1). Lowest per cent disease intensity, highest numbers of tillers, highest numbers of productive tillers per plant, highest 1000 test weight, highest yield q/ha, per cent increase yield and highest avoidable yield loss was recorded under the T₉ (seed treatment Tebuconazole 2.5g/kg of seed + two spray of Propiconazole @ 0.1%) during 2018-19. Table-1 clearly indicates that the minimum per cent disease intensity was found in T₉ (20.70%) (Seed treatment with Tebuconazole @ 2.5g/kg seed + 2 foliar spray of Tilt @ 0.1 per cent) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (22.40%), T₈ (23.20%), and T₇ (25.60%) and significantly followed by T₆ (30.90%), T₅ (32.30%), T₂ (35.80%), T₁ (30.70%) and T₃ (38.20%). Maximum per cent disease intensity (74.00%) was recorded under T₁₁ untreated (control plot) observed during second year (2019-20) of study. Earlier also Propiconazole 25 have been reported effective against spot blotch of wheat by many other workers (Rashid *et al.*, 2001; Hossain *et al.*, 2001; Patil *et al.*, 2002; Singh *et al.*, 2005; Sharma *et al.*, 2005; Shahidullah, 2006; Ahmed *et al.*,

2007; Zamal, 2007; Malaker and Mian, 2009; Rahman *et al.*, 2013) [12, 5, 11, 14, 13, 1, 19, 8, 5, 16]. Lapis (1985) [7] reported that three sprays of Propiconazole gave the best control of spot blotch and increased grain yield by 65 per cent. Mondol *et al.* (1994) [9] found that Propiconazole 25 EC (0.05 per cent) was the effective and profitable one, which controlled the disease significantly producing the high yield with maximum gross margin. Murray *et al.* (1998) [10] reported that fungicides groups like Mancozeb, Propiconazole and Tebuconazole were effective in controlling the spot blotch disease and reducing inoculum pressure. Singh and Gupta (2000) [17] have also reported that Tilt and Folicur were most effective. Singh and Singh (2007) also reported loss by this disease in the tarai region of district Balrampur in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Significant variation was found on the number of tillers per plants as a result of treatments Table-2. The maximum number of tillers per plant (10.40) was recorded in case of T₉ followed by rest treatments. Minimum number of tillers was found (6.30) on T₁₁ control plot which was statistically at par with T₄, T₆, and T₇ during first year (2018-19). Similar result were found during 2019-20.

Significant variation was found on the number of productive tillers per plants as a result of treatments (Table-2). Maximum number of productive tillers per plant (9.70) was recorded in case of T₉ which was at par with that of T₁₀ (9.40), T₈ (8.85) and T₂ (8.20). Minimum number of productive tillers was found (5.50) with T₁₁ control plot which was statistically least than rest treatments during the first year (2018-19), similar result were also noted in second year ie 2019-20.

Maximum thousand seed weight was found in T₉ (40.05 g) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (41.70 g), T₈ (39.38 g), T₄ (40.05 g), T₇ (39.38 g), T₆ (39.00g) and T₅ (38.56 g) and significantly followed by T₂ (37.00 g), T₁ (36.90 g) and T₃ (36.30g). Minimum thousand seed weight was recorded under T₁₁ (36.12 g) during the first year (2018-19). Similar findings were also noted during second year (2019-20)

It evident from Table-3 maximum yield of (39.05 q/ha) was recorded under treatment T₉ which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (38.70 q/ha), T₈ (38.55 q/ha), T₄ (37.90 q/ha) and T₇ (37.45 q/ha) and significantly followed by T₆ (34.85 q/ha), T₅ (34.70 q/ha), T₂ (33.55 q/ha), T₁ (34.30 q/ha) and T₃ (33.90 q/ha) Least grain yield q/ha recorded under T₁₁ control plot (31.85 q/ha) during 2018-19. Similar trend was noted during 2019-20 also.

Maximum per cent increase yield was found in T₉ (22.61%) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (21.51%) and T₈ (21.04%) and significantly followed by T₄ (19.00%), T₇ (17.58%), T₆ (9.42%), T₅ (8.95%), T₂ (8.48%), T₁ (7.69%), and T₃ (6.44%). Minimum percent increase yield was recorded under T₁₁ (0.00%) control, during the first year and maximum per cent increase yield was found in T₉ (24.01%) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (22.91%) and T₈ (22.43%) and significantly followed by T₄ (20.06%), T₇ (18.48%), T₆ (10.43%), T₅ (9.95%), T₂ (9.48%), T₁ (8.69%), and T₃ (7.40%). Minimum percent increase yield was recorded under T₁₁ (0.00%) control, during the second year (2019-20). During 2001-02 crop season also the treatment with Propiconazole (5.36 ton/ha) and Tebuconazole (5.26 ton/ha) provided higher yield than untreated check (Singh *et al.*, 2011).

Maximum avoidable losses was found in T₉ (18.44%) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (17.58%) and T₈ (17.28%) and significantly followed by T₄ (15.96%), T₇

(14.95%), T₆ (8.61%), T₅ (8.21%), T₂ (7.81%), T₁ (7.14%), and T₃ (5.98%). Minimum avoidable loss was recorded under T₁₁ (0.00%) control, during the first year (2018-19). Maximum avoidable losses was found in T₉ (19.36%) which was non-significantly followed by T₁₀ (18.64%) and T₈ (18.32%) and significantly followed by T₄ (16.71%), T₇ (15.60%), T₆ (9.44%), T₅ (9.05%), T₂ (8.66%), T₁ (7.99%), and T₃ (6.91%). Minimum avoidable loss was recorded under T₁₁ (0.00%) control, during the second year (2019-20). Result of a multi-locational test conducted nation wise during 1997-

98 and 1998-99 reveal highest yield losses of 50.6 per cent, at Dharwad, 40.9 per cent at Faizabad and 27.0 per cent at Gordaspur during 1998-99 (Singh *et al.*, 2002)^[15]. In Nepal, it was shown that spot blotch induced grain yield losses of 52% under soil nutrient stress comrade with 26% under optimum fertilization and spot blotch continues to causes substantial grain yield reductions under resource-limited farming conditions (Sharma and Duveillar 2006)^[14]. In farmers' fields in Bangladesh, the average losses due to these foliar blights were estimated to be 15 per cent (Alam *et al.*, 1997)^[2].

Table 1: Impact of different fungicides and bio-agent against foliar blight disease of wheat 2018-19 and 2019-20

S.N.	Treatment	Date of Disease appearance	PDI 2018-19			Date of Disease appearance	PDI 2019-20		
			Before spray	After I spray	After II spray		Before spray	After I spray	After II spray
T ₁	Thiram	04/02/19	14.30(6.10)	31.82(27.80)	37.52(31.10)	04/02/20	13.31(5.30)	31.88(27.90)	37.29(30.70)
T ₂	Raxil	03/02/19	11.24(3.80)	30.79(26.20)	36.63(35.60)	04/02/20	10.94(3.60)	30.98(26.50)	36.75 (35.80)
T ₃	<i>T. virde</i>	03/02/19	15.45(7.10)	33.21(30.00)	38.41(36.80)	05/02/20	15.34(7.00)	33.15(29.90)	38.17 (38.20)
T ₄	Nativo	30/01/19	20.09(11.80)	25.77 (18.90)	29.60(24.40)	29/01/20	20.00(11.70)	25.70(18.80)	36.03(34.60)
T ₅	Jeevamrit	31/01/19	18.24(9.80)	29.53 (24.30)	34.94 (32.80)	01/02/20	18.24(9.80)	28.79 (23.20)	34.63 (32.30)
T ₆	Copper oxychloride	26/01/19	21.72(13.70)	30.46 (25.70)	34.08 (31.40)	27/01/20	21.56 (13.50)	30.33 (25.50)	33.77(30.90)
T ₇	Hexaconazole	01/02/19	20.96(5.80)	26.57 (20.00)	30.46 (25.70)	31/01/20	20.62 (12.40)	26.42(19.80)	30.40 (25.60)
T ₈	T ₁ + T ₄	04/02/19	13.94(5.80)	24.35(17.00)	29.06 (23.60)	05/02/20	13.69(5.60)	24.04 (16.60)	28.79(23.20)
T ₉	T ₂ + Tilt	05/02/19	10.63(3.40)	22.46(14.60)	27.27 (21.00)	05/02/20	10.30(3.20)	21.56(13.50)	27.06 (20.70)
T ₁₀	T ₃ + Folicur	02/02/19	15.12(6.80)	23.18 (15.50)	28.32 (22.50)	04/02/20	14.65(6.40)	23.03(15.30)	28.25 (22.40)
T ₁₁	Control	20/01/19	22.54 (14.70)	45.46 (50.80)	57.92(71.80)	18/01/20	23.03 (15.30)	46.61(52.80)	59.34 (74.00)
	S.Em±		0.86	1.30	1.55		0.81	1.18	1.74
	CD (p=0.05)		2.54	3.86	4.59		2.40	3.51	5.16

Table 2: Impact of different fungicides and bio-agent on Numbers of tillers per plant and number of productive tillers per plant

S.N.	Treatment	2018-19		2019-20	
		No. of Tillers per plant	No. of productive tillers per plant	No. of Tillers per plant	No. of productive tillers per plant
T ₁	Thiram	8.20	7.60	8.30	7.70
T ₂	Raxil	9.00	8.20	9.10	8.30
T ₃	<i>T. virde</i>	8.00	7.40	8.15	7.55
T ₄	Nativo	7.20	6.80	7.30	6.90
T ₅	Jeevamrit	7.30	6.76	7.45	6.85
T ₆	Copper oxychloride	6.90	6.25	7.00	6.35
T ₇	Hexaconazole	7.00	6.55	7.20	6.60
T ₈	T ₁ + T ₄	9.60	8.85	9.80	9.00
T ₉	T ₂ + Tilt	10.40	9.70	10.50	9.80
T ₁₀	T ₃ + Folicur	10.10	9.40	10.25	9.50
T ₁₁	Control	6.30	5.50	6.40	5.56
	S.Em±	0.36	0.35	0.34	0.33
	CD (p=0.05)	1.06	1.05	1.01	0.98

Table 3: Impact of different fungicides and bio-agent on test weight, grain yield,% increase yield over control and avoidable losses on wheat

S.N.	Treatment	2018-19				2019-20			
		Test weight	Grain yield (q/ha)	% increase yield	Avoidable losses	Test weight	Grain yield (q/ha)	% increase yield	Avoidable losses
T ₁	Thiram	36.90	34.30	7.69	7.14	36.95	34.40	8.69	7.99
T ₂	Raxil	37.00	34.55	8.48	7.81	37.30	34.65	9.48	8.66
T ₃	<i>T. virde</i>	36.30	33.90	6.44	6.05	37.15	34.00	7.42	6.91
T ₄	Nativo	40.05	37.90	19.00	15.96	40.25	38.00	20.06	16.71
T ₅	Jeevamrit	38.56	34.70	8.95	8.21	38.80	34.80	9.95	9.05
T ₆	Copper oxychloride	39.00	34.85	9.42	8.61	39.20	34.95	10.43	9.44
T ₇	Hexaconazole	39.38	37.45	17.58	14.95	39.70	37.50	18.48	15.60
T ₈	T ₁ + T ₄	40.95	38.55	21.04	17.38	41.20	38.75	22.43	18.32
T ₉	T ₂ + Tilt	42.05	39.05	22.61	18.44	42.40	39.25	24.01	19.36
T ₁₀	T ₃ + Folicur	41.70	38.70	21.51	17.70	41.75	38.90	22.91	18.64
T ₁₁	Control	36.12	31.85	0.00	0.00	36.18	31.65	0.00	0.00
	S.Em±	1.43	1.61	0.55	0.62	1.98	1.55	0.72	0.64
	CD (p=0.05)	4.26	4.79	1.63	1.84	5.89	4.60	2.14	1.90

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